

FANTASTIC TOOLS IN CREATIVITY OF DORIS LESSING**Shodmanova Shokhida Alisherovna****Uzbek State University of World Languages,
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Abstract: the article aims at defining Doris Lessing's major approaches to writing in the genre of science fiction through the 70's of the XXth c. Artistic, aesthetic and philosophical elements have been disclosed and analyzed. They pertain to artistic world creation in the short story "Report on the Threatened City" (1972).

Keywords: D. Lessing, short fiction, science fiction, artistic world creation, Sufism, "Report on the Threatened City", moral choice.

Literary landscape of the 60-70s. The twentieth century is characterized by the flourishing of the genre of English-language science fiction. During this period, literary critics begin to use the term "New Wave" in relation to authors whose work is marked by avant-garde, radical and eclectic elements. Outstanding Australian science fiction writer Damien Broderick noted that this literary movement was a reaction "to the depletion of a genre that lacks a formal definition." The term itself was introduced into scientific circulation by the English writer Christopher Priest, author of the collection *Endless Summer*.

The London-based magazine *New Worlds* was a creative platform for representatives of experimental science fiction. This periodical published works by prominent English science fiction writers Michael Moorcock, James Ballard, Edwin Tab Brian Aldiss, John Brunner. Representatives of the new direction rethought the specifics of the genre, the logic of its form, style and aesthetics.

In this context, it is worth noting that the departure from the established canons of science fiction with its emphasis on logic, reason and common sense was perceived negatively by many literary critics. For example, the famous English novelist and poet Kingsley Amis (1922–1995) critically notes the presence of "elements of shock, manipulation of typographical means, one-sentence paragraphs, strained metaphors, vagueness in content, Eastern religious beliefs, and leftist ideological postulates."

The connection with the eastern moral and ethical teaching of Sufism is clearly visible in the work of D. Lessing, which dates back to the 70s. XX century . The English writer emphasizes the need for integrity and active moral choice. This choice, according to the famous American researcher Nancy Topping Bezin , is aimed at "achieving the perfection of the inner world through unity with others and nature." The integrity and interdependence of such a reality is opposed to an inevitable catastrophe. The moral and ethical teaching of Sufism assumes an ontological dimension of integrity and operates with images of "the human soul in search and approach to the state of ultimate harmony and integration with all living things." It is this type of search that the English writer offers in her small prose works of the period under study.

In the story "Report on the City" (1972), D. Lessing defines the importance of achieving personal, social and cosmic unity. The complexity of the implementation of this plan lies in the "inability and unwillingness of the Western patriarchal society to view the world through the prism of the plurality of subcultures and phenomena of the human universe." The measurement of the inner personality in D. Lessing's story is equated with the sacred possibilities of a person's creative potential.

The need to change the established patterns of one's own attitude and behavior provokes painful reactions and resistance during the transition to a state of internal unity. The unwillingness of the inhabitants of the city to accept information about the inevitability of a catastrophe clearly demonstrates their passive perception of death, not only of their own, but of many thousands of their own kind. The American cultural anthropologist Ernest Becker notes in his seminal work *Denial of Death* (1974) that the deepest need of the human being is manifested in "getting rid of the fear of death and non-existence that life brings." The recognition of a catastrophe, according to this definition, is a statement of the crisis of one's own identity and the recognition of the ineffectiveness of old approaches. Consequently, people are doomed to a limited existence due to the impossibility of overcoming existential challenges.

It should be noted that the work lacks a detailed description of the main characters. According to B. Drain , most of the characters " are depicted statically, there is no personal

and mental development." Noteworthy is the absence of a central character as such in this story. In that sense, *The City Report* lives up to the norms of science fiction. The thematic content of this genre is more about the common fate of a large number of people than personal transformations at the level of individual individuals. The key task of this approach is the need to cover wide time and space horizons.

The story "Report on the City" is a summary of the history of mankind: wars, ideological dogmas, living conditions and natural disasters. Numerous inserts from periodicals and television programs give the reader a separate vision of earthly existence. The interweaving of these two ways of narration is clearly visible in the textual fabric. The plurality of views is achieved through the use of typographical means. Alien and human visions are presented in a contrasting set of fonts and differ in editing tools. Such a combined presentation of the material makes possible frequent transitions between narrative planes.

In the 70s. D. Lessing's work actively includes elements of science fiction. At the same time, the approaches of the English writer to text formation in the works of this period are distinguished by their departure from the established canons of science fiction with its emphasis on logic, reason and empirical data. The moral and ethical principles of Sufism come to the fore, which involve the measurement of internal integrity and harmony. Pluralism of views, interpretations and readings, in the opinion of D. Lessing, should help the reader form an objective vision of the world.

Literature :

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